

Fracture mechanism and strength prediction of in-situ TiB₂/Al composite

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Introduction

- Particle reinforced aluminum matrix composites (PRAMCs) have attracted extensive attention and research effort for their higher specific strength, fatigue resistance and wear resistance than the corresponding parent metals.
- However, the micro-structure and damage-fracture mechanism of PRAMCs are more complex than those of their parent metals. The damage mechanism during fracture needs to be fully explored and described with appropriate constitutive model to characterize the deformation, damage and fracture process, so as to promote their application in engineering structures.
- Traditional PRAMCs, abbreviated to ex-PRAMCs, are usually fabricated by externally adding particles into metal with physical methods such as powder metallurgy and liquid stirring casting. In-situ PRAMCs are usually fabricated by precipitating in-situ particles from molten metal via chemical reaction, such as the mixed salt reaction method, which are of much smaller and regular particles and stronger particle-matrix interface than those of the ex-PRAMCs.
- The mechanical properties and fracture process of PRAMCs are seriously affected by the elastic-plastic fracture behavior of matrix, the strength of the particles and particle-matrix interface.
- Damage modes of PRAMCs
 - Particle brittle cracking
 - Particle-matrix interface debonding
 - Ductile failure of the matrix
 - modes coexist and one or two of them dominant.

The ductile-brittle meso-constitutive model

Ductile-brittle damage constitutive model

- Mori-Tanaka homogenization technique
 - Porous metal plasticity model for matrix
 - Gurson-Tvergaard-Needleman (GTN) model
 - Isotropic hardened, Ludwik power law
- $$\Phi = \left(\frac{\sigma_{eq}}{\bar{\sigma}_{mf}} \right)^2 + 2q_1 f^* \cosh \left(\frac{3q_2 \sigma_H}{2\bar{\sigma}_{mf}} \right) - (1 + q_1^2 f^{*2}) = 0$$
- Elastic-brittle model for particle
 - Isotropic, linear elastic $R_i(\sigma_i) = 1 - \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\sigma_i}{S_0} \right)^m \right]$
 - Brittle fracture
 - Maximum principal stress failure criterion
 - Statistical damage model-Weibull Probability Model

Experimental & Simulation

- Smooth round bar with diameter of 9mm;
- Notched round bars with diameter of 9mm and radii of 4 & 8mm;
 - Gauge length of the extensometer of 25mm;
 - Deformation is the extension of extensometer;
- Fracture morphology
 - Dimple
 - Fractured particle cluster
 - Particles in dimple
- Radial return algorithm;
- Backward Euler integration algorithm;
- Newton iteration;
- Eshelby tensor;
- The tangent operators
 - Elastic
 - Mises plasticity
 - GTN model

Discussion and Conclusion

- The smaller the notch radius, the more frequent the particle fracture occurs and the faster the particle volume reduces;
- The particles volume fraction at the edge point E is always lower than that of the central point C, which results from the observation that particle maximum principle stress at point E is always larger than that at point C when the tensile elongation is smaller than 0.06mm. Beyond this stage of deformation, the particles volume fraction at point E has already reduced to zero. The increase of the equivalent plastic strain in matrix is closely related to the increase of particle principal stress and the reduction of particle volume fraction;
- The particle volume fraction reduction at point E is much slower for R8;
- The void volume fraction is higher at the middle section for R4;
- At the early stage of deformation, the evolution of void volume is mainly caused by the voids nucleation, which occurs earlier at edge point E. With the increase of deformation, the particle nucleation has come to an end and the material enters the intermediate deformation stage during which the void volume fraction increase steadily. Then, at the last stage of deformation, the void growth is boosted and the void coalescence results in the final fracture of the minimum section. At the intermediate and the last stage of deformation, the void volume fraction at point C is always larger than that of point E, which indicates that the micro cracks firstly arise at the very center of the specimens.

- A ductile-brittle damage constitutive model is proposed.
- The smaller notch radius corresponds to faster particle fracture, void nucleation and void growth, and smaller tensile deformation at fracture.